

**ABKÜRZUNGEN IN WISSENSCHAFTLICHEN TEXTEN:
HERAUSFORDERUNGEN DER ÜBERSETZUNG
ZWISCHEN FACH- UND ALLTAGSSPRACHE /**

**ABBREVIATIONS IN ACADEMIC TEXTS: CHALLENGES
OF TRANSLATION BETWEEN SPECIALIZED AND EVERYDAY LANGUAGE**

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This research explores the use and translation of abbreviations in specialized and everyday language, focusing on German and Romanian. It discusses linguistic economy, context sensitivity, and stylistic and cultural variation. Special emphasis is placed on academic communication and the interlingual transfer of abbreviations. The study highlights the need for standardization through abbreviation lists to avoid misinterpretation. By analyzing common patterns and differences, the article aims to provide practical guidelines for the consistent and norm-compliant use of abbreviations in scholarly texts, promoting clarity, terminological precision, and mutual understanding across languages and academic disciplines.